

Research Article

Gamified Learning in Technical Education: Evaluating the Effectiveness of Roblox-Based Aircraft Maintenance Simulation

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Abstract: In today's technology-driven world, where engaging and meaningful learning experiences are regarded as highly effective, incorporating technology into education is critical. Roblox Aircraft Maintenance Aeroskill exemplifies this approach by combining education and gaming to create an immersive experience based on aircraft maintenance principles. Although technology-based learning is becoming more popular, gaming's potential to improve aviation education remains largely untapped. This project seeks to address this gap by investigating the impact of Roblox Aircraft Maintenance Aeroskill on aviation education, particularly among young people. The game teaches users the fundamentals of aircraft maintenance through an interactive Roblox environment, as well as hands-on experiences in a simulated setting. Initial testing has yielded promising results, with players demonstrating a greater understanding of aircraft systems and maintenance procedures. According to the post survey 64.7% of total respondents agreed that the Roblox Aeroskill was easy to navigate. The game's structure promotes self-directed learning and introduces young people to critical skills, sparking an early interest in aviation maintenance careers which promotes the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG4-Quality Education). The findings of this project indicate that Roblox Aircraft Maintenance Aeroskill has the potential to improve both traditional and online aviation education by making learning more accessible and enjoyable. Future initiatives are encouraged to investigate similar gaming elements in aviation curricula, fostering collaboration between educators and developers to create engaging educational tools that address a variety of learning needs.

Keywords: Roblox, Aircraft Maintenance, Aviation Education

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1. INTRODUCTION

The global aviation industry continues to experience significant growth, driven by technological advancements and increasing demand for air travel. However, this growth is not mirrored in the education pipeline, where a critical talent gap exists, particularly in aviation maintenance sectors. According to the International Air Transport Association (IATA), a large portion of the global youth population lacks access to aviation-related education opportunities, which in turn affects the availability of skilled talent in the airline and maintenance workforce. Despite the exciting career prospects and technological developments in aviation, young individuals—especially those under 18—show limited interest in entering the field (Brownlow, 2022).

One promising approach to address this issue is through the gamification of education—merging learning content with interactive digital environments. Roblox, a widely-used game development platform among youth, has emerged as an accessible and engaging tool for educational simulations (Haskins, 2022; Roblox, n.d.). Inspired by this, the *Roblox Aircraft Maintenance Aeroskill* project was developed to bridge the educational gap by offering a virtual, game-based learning environment that simulates real-world aircraft maintenance scenarios. This aligns with the objectives of Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG4) — ensuring inclusive and equitable quality education and promoting lifelong learning opportunities for all.

The main objective of this study is to evaluate the potential of *Roblox Aircraft Maintenance Aeroskill* in increasing awareness, interest, and basic understanding of aircraft maintenance principles among young learners. It investigates how immersive gamified learning can serve as an early intervention strategy to inspire interest in aviation-related education, particularly in maintenance engineering. By doing so, it contributes to the long-term sustainability of the aviation workforce and explores the viability of integrating game-based learning into formal curricula for technical education (CAE, n.d.; L3Harris, n.d.; Florida Flyers, 2024).

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

This chapter outlines the research methodology employed in the development of the Roblox Aircraft Maintenance Aeroskill simulation. The methodology includes the design and development process, as well as the software tools used to create and implement the simulation as stated on Figure 1.

Figure 1: Overall Flow chart of Roblox Aircraft Maintenance Aeroskill.

The development process for the *Roblox Aircraft Maintenance Aeroskill* simulation is divided into the following stages. The first stage involves defining the objectives of the simulation, identifying the key aircraft maintenance tasks to be simulated, and designing the user experience. The focus is on

creating an educational platform that can help users understand and practice essential aircraft maintenance procedures. During this stage, the design of the maintenance building, aircraft components, and interactive elements is planned. Next, 3D Modeling and Asset Creation Using Blender is used. 3D models of the aircraft parts and the maintenance environment are created. These models are designed to be as realistic as possible, ensuring that they reflect real-world counterparts in terms of size, shape, and functionality. Each component, such as engines, wings, landing gear, and maintenance tools, is modeled with high attention to detail. Textures and animations are also applied to the models in Blender to enhance their realism.

The third stage involve importing models to Roblox Studio. Once the 3D models are completed in Blender, they are imported into Roblox Studio for integration into the simulation environment. Roblox Studio enables the positioning and scaling of models to create a cohesive and navigable environment. It also supports scripting to add interactivity, allowing users to perform tasks such as engine inspections, part replacements, and system diagnostics. The fourth is Scripting and Interaction. The interactivity of the simulation is implemented using Lua, the scripting language in Roblox Studio. Scripts are written to trigger specific actions within the simulation, such as opening maintenance panels, replacing parts, and triggering animations for maintenance tasks. The interaction model is designed to be intuitive, with clear instructions guiding users through each task. The simulation is also programmed to provide feedback, such as task completion indicators and performance evaluations.

The fifth element is testing and refinement. After the initial development, the simulation undergoes rigorous testing to ensure that it functions as intended. This stage involves both functional testing, to check that all interactive elements work correctly, and user testing, to assess the ease of use and educational value. Feedback from test users is incorporated to improve the simulation’s interface, task flow, and overall user experience. Finally, is the Sixth is deployment and evaluation. Once the simulation is fully developed and refined, it is deployed on the Roblox platform for use by the target audience. The effectiveness of the simulation in teaching aircraft maintenance procedures is evaluated through user feedback and performance metrics. Users’ ability to complete tasks and learn from the simulation is assessed to determine the success of the project and to identify areas for future improvement.

2.1 Software Tools and Platforms

The development of the Roblox Aircraft Maintenance Aeroskill simulation involves the use of several key software tools, each playing a vital role in creating the interactive simulation. These tools as stated on Table 1.

Table 1: Compilation of Software used for Roblox Aeroskill Development.

Decription	Software
Roblox: The main platform to market and distribute our simulation.	
Roblox studio: To develop Aircraft Maintenance Simulation Aeroskill and import our 3D designs of the components.	

Blender: The platform to 3D design the required components, aircraft parts and maintenance building.	
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Roblox

Roblox serves as the primary platform for the distribution and interaction of the simulation. The platform is chosen due to its widespread accessibility, allowing users to engage with the simulation directly. Roblox provides a user-friendly interface and robust online features, making it suitable for reaching a broad audience, including students and professionals interested in aircraft maintenance training. The platform supports multiplayer features, which enhances the collaborative learning experience within the simulation.

Roblox Studio

Roblox Studio is the development environment used to design and implement the Aeroskill simulation. It allows for the creation of interactive elements such as aircraft maintenance tasks, educational modules, and user interfaces. In Roblox Studio, scripting and testing are done to ensure that the simulation's features work seamlessly. The platform also facilitates the importation of 3D models and assets, ensuring that the virtual environment closely mirrors real-life aircraft maintenance procedures. Roblox Studio's scripting language, Lua, was utilized to program the interaction between the user and the virtual components.

Blender

Blender is employed for the 3D design and modeling of the various components needed for the simulation, such as aircraft parts, maintenance tools, and the maintenance building itself. Blender allows for the creation of high-quality, realistic models that are imported into Roblox Studio for integration into the simulation. The 3D design process in Blender involves detailed modeling, texturing, and animation, which ensures that the simulation's visual elements are both functional and visually accurate. Blender's compatibility with Roblox Studio ensures smooth transitions from the design phase to the implementation phase.

3. FINDINGS

The Roblox Aircraft Maintenance Aeroskill project is specifically designed to boost students' understanding and awareness of the aircraft maintenance field, providing an interactive and realistic look into the daily tasks and responsibilities within this sector. Players can simulate a range of typical maintenance tasks, such as line maintenance refueling, replacing landing gear wheels, conducting walk-around inspections, and other critical routines that ensure aircraft are safe and operational. By replicating these real-world tasks, the project serves as an accessible, gamified entry point for students to gain hands-on experience and develop an appreciation for the technical skills involved in aviation maintenance.

3.1 Product Structure

The game educates players about basic aircraft maintenance procedures, emphasising effective learning, realistic experiences, and knowledge acquisition in a virtual hangar environment. A hangar, a large structure used to store, maintain, and house aircraft, is an ideal setting for inspections and

maintenance. This immersive setting is intended to pique the interest and engagement of school- aged students, making the field of aircraft maintenance more appealing and accessible as Figure 2.

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Figure 2: Map Structure.

This is the structure of the Roblox Aircraft Maintenance Aeroskill game environment, which is divided into two major servers: Server 1 and Server 2. Each server hosts different sections of the game, which represent different areas in the virtual environment designed to simulate real-world aviation facilities. Server 1 contains the Office and Hangar areas or base maintenance, while Server 2 houses the Airport section or line maintenance, resulting in a segmented layout for easy navigation and resource management as Figure 3.

Figure 3: Server 1 Office.

Server 1 manages the office and hangar environments. The Office section is where players should start. Users can move from the Office to the Hangar, where they can perform more hands-on technical aircraft maintenance tasks, such as landing gear change procedure. This organisation enables the game to effectively separate administrative and hands-on activities, increasing the realism of moving between different parts of a maintenance facility as Figure 4.

Figure 4: Server 1 Hangar.

Server 2 runs on its own and is solely dedicated to the airport or line maintenance. This section could be used for activities such as ground operations, refuelling, and walkaround inspection. By placing the Airport on a separate server, the game can efficiently handle the high traffic and unique processes associated with the airport environment without overburdening Server 1. This layout allows players to experience both the technical and operational aspects of aviation, providing a comprehensive understanding of aircraft maintenance and operations as Figure 5.

Figure 5: Server 2 Line Maintenance on Apron Area.

3.2 Detailed Aircraft Components and Task

Players navigate through visually rich environments where they can actively inspect and interact with detailed representations of specific aircraft parts, which are the Cockpit Control, engine, landing gear, pitot tube, wing, and ram air turbine. This not only involves visual observation but also interactive elements like clicking or interacting with controls to delve deeper into each aircraft part as figure 6 and 7.

Figure 6: Detail Aircraft Component.

Figure 7: Cockpit Control.

4. DISCUSSION

The goal of this project is to address Malaysia's aviation talent shortage by encouraging young people to express an early interest in aviation maintenance careers. This project's goal is to introduce school leavers, teenagers, and children to the fundamentals of aircraft maintenance in an engaging, accessible manner by developing Roblox Aircraft Maintenance Aeroskill, an interactive game on the popular platform Roblox. This project aims to bridge the gap in exposure to aviation careers by providing an immersive experience that simulates real-world aviation maintenance tasks, sparking curiosity and encouraging young users to learn more about the field and reflect the quality education SDG-4 concept.

This project aims to contribute to the aviation industry's long-term viability by training a new generation of skilled professionals. By raising awareness of aviation maintenance careers, it hopes to bridge the gap between industry demand and available talent, ensuring a consistent supply of qualified individuals in the future. This project also investigates the potential of gaming as an educational tool, demonstrating how technology can be used to improve learning and career development in technical especially in aircraft maintenance. In order to evaluate the usability of Roblox Aircraft Maintenance Aeroskill, a simple post survey has been conducted and 17 sample students have been chosen from first semester Diploma Aircraft Maintenance as Figure 8.

How well did the Roblox Aeroskill simulation help you understand the aircraft maintenance procedure as general?

17 responses

Figure 8: Post-Survey of Roblox Aircraft Maintenance Aeroskill.

The survey results show that Roblox Aircraft Maintenance Aeroskill considerably improves the effectiveness of aviation instruction by efficiently simplifying and communicating complicated aircraft repair ideas to students. According to the first graph, 47.1% of respondents gave the simulation the highest possible score (5), showing a strong consensus that it helped them learn general aircraft maintenance processes. Furthermore, 23.5% gave it a 4, supporting the excellent feedback. Together, this accounts for more than 70% of participants recognising the simulation's effectiveness in meeting its teaching objectives.

This high level of agreement demonstrates how Roblox Aircraft Maintenance Aeroskill simplifies the learning process by converting complex technical procedures into an approachable and engaging style. The simulation uses gamification to attract learners' attention and teach complex aviation concepts in a visual, step-by-step format that is easier to understand than traditional textbook or lecture-based methods. This interactive technique not only makes learning more enjoyable, but it also improves information retention by having users actively participate in simulated maintenance activities.

5. CONCLUSION

Development Of Roblox Aircraft Maintenance Aeroskill focused on aircraft maintenance to increase student enrolment in related courses. The project had been succeed as an interactive and immersive learning environment in which users, particularly young audiences, can discover the foundations of aircraft maintenance in an entertaining manner. The simulation, which gamifies aviation education, produces a one-of-a-kind platform that piques students' interest in the topic.

The use of Roblox, a popular platform among teens, guarantees that the simulation is effectively delivered to its intended audience. Through games, pupils can get a rudimentary understanding of maintenance processes and aviation concepts, sparking an early interest in studying aviation-related courses. This is consistent with my goal of expanding enrolment by closing the gap between education and entertainment. The poll results support the potential viability of this method, as the majority of respondents believe that aviation education on gaming platforms is useful.

Roblox Aircraft Maintenance Aeroskill serves as a promotional tool for aviation courses, making the subject more accessible and enticing to school leavers. As students get more familiar with aircraft maintenance principles through simulation, they may be more likely to enrol in formal courses to further their expertise and pursue a career in the sector. By integrating education and innovation, my project helps to develop the future generation of aviation professionals.

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References

- Brownlow, J. (2022, September 23). *Why aren't young people joining the aviation industry?* World Aviation Festival. <https://worldaviationfestival.com/blog/airlines/what-is-holding-young-people-back-from-joining-the-aviation-industry/>
- CAE. (n.d.). *Maintenance training systems*. <https://www.cae.com/defense-security/what-we-do/training-systems/maintenance-training-systems>

Florida Flyers Flight Academy. (2024, January 15). *Aircraft maintenance: Ultimate trends 2024*.

<https://www.flightschoolusa.com/aircraft-maintenance-ultimate-trends-2024/>

Haskins, H. (2022). *Roblox 101: Everything you need to know about the game-creation platform*. PCMag.

<https://www.pcmag.com/how-to/roblox-101-everything-you-need-to-know-about-the-game-creation-platform>

International Air Transport Association (IATA). (n.d.). *IATA future airline industry*.

<https://www.iata.org/contentassets/086e8361b2f4423e88166845afdd2f03/iata-future-airline-industry.pdf>

L3Harris Technologies. (n.d.). *Virtual maintenance trainer*. <https://www.l3harris.com/all-capabilities/virtual-maintenance-trainer>

Roblox. (n.d.). *Start learning with tutorials – Roblox Creator Hub*. <https://create.roblox.com/docs/tutorials>